

N-ligands and their Transition Metal Complexes: Part IV. Ultra-violet Absorption Spectra of *vic*-dioximes

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Derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2,3-dioxime are prepared and their ultra-violet absorption spectra are investigated in different solvents.

In continuation of our work on oxime ketones¹, oxime hydrazones², oxime nitriles^{3a} and oxime imines^{3b}, we now report our work on *vic*-dioximes. The present paper deals with the preparation and the ultra-violet absorption spectra of the derivatives of 2,3 dioxobutyric acid 2, 3 dioxime (I)

These dioximes are considered to have preferentially the anti-configuration (II).

The ultra-violet absorption spectral characteristics (λ_{max} and E_M) of these dioximes and of 2,3-butane dione dioxime in water, methanol and sodium hydroxide solutions are recorded in Table I.

The ultra-violet absorption spectra of *vic*-dioximes have been investigated by Barany Braude and Pianka⁴, Borello and Catino⁵, Dave and Talati⁶ Banks *et al*⁷, and Bambanek and Pflaum⁸.

Chromophore:—The intense absorption band (K) at 230-47 m μ observed in the case of derivatives of 2,3 dioxobutyric acid 2,3 dioxime in aqueous and alcoholic solutions is considered to be $\pi \longleftrightarrow \pi^*$ transition and is attributed to the crossed conjugated system.

1. A. M. Talati, P. M. Desai and T. I. Patel, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, **27**, 159.
2. A. M. Talati and P. M. Desai., *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 677.
3. A. M. Talati and T. I. Patel, *ibid.* (a) 1964, **41**, 602; (b) communicated.
4. H. C., Barany, E. A. Braude and M. Planka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1898.
5. E. Borello and A. Catino, *Ann. Chim., (Italy)* 1956, **46**, 571.
6. J. S. Dave and A. M. Talati, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **900**, 1952.
7. (a) Banks and Carlson, *Ann. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **7**, 291.
(b) Banks, Hooker and Richard, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **29**, 550.
8. M. A. Bambanek and R. T. Pflaum., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 289.

TABLE I

(III)

X=	Compound (III) where			In H O		In Me OH		In NaOH	
	Y=	Z=	λ_{max} ($m\mu$)	E_m	max ($m\mu$)	E_m	λ_{max} ($m\mu$)	E_m	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCO}$	H	H	233-34	19820	236-38	25030	271-74	33370	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{Me})\text{CO}$	H	H	230	14940	230-34	16770	278	19130	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}$	H	H	231-32	12420	231-32	11530	276-78	19050	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{Me})\text{CO}$	H	Me	242	17170	239-40	16330	280	24660	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{Me})\text{CO}$	Me	Me	245-47	21810	245-47	26620	245-47	20580	
Me	H	H	226-27	13880	227	18250	265-67	19770	

Since the absorption bands of 2, 3 butanedione monoxime¹ and 2, 3 butane dione dioxime in alcohol are at 227-29 $m\mu$ and 227 $m\mu$ respectively, the replacement of the carbonyl group by an oxime group in a position adjacent to another oxime group causes almost no shift in the absorption band. Further introduction of a carboxyl group (ester or anilide) which extends the conjugation in a crossed manner, causes a red shift of 4-5 $m\mu$ in case of ester and of 6-11 $m\mu$ in case of anilide.

The second band (X) observed at 272-86 $m\mu$ in case of *vic*-oxime ketones in water is not observed in case of *vic*-dioximes in aqueous or alcoholic solutions. This band has been attributed¹ to their ionic tautomer existing in those solutions. The absence of X-band in aqueous or alcoholic solutions of the *vic*-dioximes is considered to suggest that they are largely present in the chelated or associated form in these solutions.

To decide between association (solute-solute interaction) and chelation (intermolecular H-bonding), the molecular weights of 2,3-dioxo-butyranilide 2,3-dioxime and 2,3 butane dione dioxime were determined by Rast method.

The molecular weights are:

Compound	Molecular wt. found	Molecular wt. calculated for monomer
2,3-dioxo-butyranilide	218	221
2,3-dioxime	216 222	
2,3-butane dione dioxime	119 117 116	116

The results are indicative of the non-existence of any dimers of these compounds in boiling camphor solution.

Another piece of evidence is provided by the study of optical densities of these compounds over a range of concentrations in methanol at fixed wavelengths. The results are presented in Table II. It is suggested from these results that the molecules of these dioximes are largely in the chelated form in solution.

TABLE II

2,3-dioxobutyranilide 2,3-dioxime in methanol		2,3 butane dione dioxime in methanol	
C(mg/l)	$\lambda = 237 \text{ m}\mu$ $E_m \times 10^{-3}$	C(mg/l)	$\lambda = 227 \text{ m}\mu$ $E_m \times 10^{-3}$
1.32	24.4	0.74	16.6
2.64	25.0	1.48	16.2
3.96	25.2	2.42	16.5
5.28	25.1	2.96	16.4
6.66	25.6	3.70	16.6
7.92	24.8	4.44	16.4
9.24	25.4	5.18	16.7
		5.92	16.4
		6.66	16.4
		7.40	16.3

Substitution effect:

The replacement of the ester group by anilide group causes a red shift. This may be attributed to the influence of phenyl group affecting the conjugation. This is in agreement with the observations of Dave and Talati⁶ that the substitution in the benzene ring causes a marked shift of the absorption band of the dioximes.

Methylation of the anilide causes a blue shift of 3-6 $\text{m}\mu$ of the K-band. This shift may be attributed to the opening of chelate ring involving anilide group and the steric effect of methyl group. Similar results have been obtained with naphthol-AS⁹. It is observed that in relation to the absorption spectra of naphthol-AS, that of its N-methyl derivative shows a marked hypsochromic effect and is attributed to its non-formation of the chelate ring.

Methylation of oxime groups : when alpha-oxime group is methylated, a red shift of 6-9 $\text{m}\mu$ is observed. When both oxime groups are methylated, a total red shift of 13-15 $\text{m}\mu$ is observed. This is in agreement with the observations of Borello and Catino⁵.

Solvent effect :

When we compare the absorption band of the *vic*-dioxime in methanol to that in aqueous solution, we find that the band is almost unshifted or shifted slightly (3-4 $\text{m}\mu$) to a shorter wavelength with increase in the dielectric constant of the solvent. This indicates the absence of solute-solvent interaction and the possibility of a chelate ring involving the oxime and anilide groups.

Further, in case of 2,3 dioxo N-methyl butyranilide 2,3-dioxime 2-methyl ether, we find a red shift of the absorption band when polarity of the solvent is increased. Hence it is considered that alpha-oxime group is largely responsible for H-bonding in chelation and that on methylation of that group solute-solvent interaction is observed, beta-oxime group not providing alternative path for intra-molecular H-bonding. In case of 2,3-dioxo N-methyl butyranilide 2,3-dioxime dimethyl ether the absorption band remains unshifted when the polarity of the solvent is increased.

Alkali effect :

The X-band is observed in the region of 265-80 μ in alkali solutions. It may be attributed to their ionic tautomeric forms. This X-band is not observed in case of 2,3-dioxo N-methyl butyranilide 2,3-dioxime dimethyl ether which would not ionise. The X-band is observed in case of both 2,3-dioxo N-methyl butyranilide 2,3-dioxime and its 2-methyl ether. Hence it is suggested that both oxime groups would be capable of ionisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dioximes of 2,3-dioxo butyranilide, 2,3-dioxo butyr-N-methyl anilide and ethyl dioxobutyrate were prepared from acetoacetanilide, acetoacet-N-methylanilide and ethyl acetoacetate by the method of Dave and Talati⁶. 2,3-dioxobutyryl-N-methyl anilide 2,3-dioxime 2-methyl ether was similarly prepared from 2,3-dioxobutyryl-N-methylanilide 2-oxime methyl ether and was methylated by dimethyl sulphate to dimethyl ether. 2,3-butane dione dioxime was a commercial sample (C.P. grade). All products (colourless) were crystallised from dilute alcohol. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

X=	Compound (III) where		m.p. obs. °C	m.p. lit. °C	%N found	%N calc.
	Y=	Z=				
C ₆ H ₅ NHCO	H	H	192	192 ⁶	—	—
C ₆ H ₅ N (Me)CO	H	H	210	—	17.6	18.0
C ₂ H ₅ OCO	H	H	130	130 ¹⁰	—	—
C ₆ H ₅ N(Me) CO	H	Me	141	—	17.4	16.9
C ₆ H ₅ N (Me) CO	Me	Me	182-3	—	16.6	16.0
Me	H	H	238-9	234-40 ¹¹	—	—

Ultra-violet absorption spectra in water, methanol and sodium hydroxide solutions were investigated with Beckman Model DU spectrophotometer using matched 1 cm. quartz cell.

Mol. wts. were determined by a semi-micro Rast method using camphor.

Thanks are due to Prof. S. M. Sethna for his kind interest in the work and to Dr. S. S. Lele for microanalysis (% N) of the samples. One of us (P.M.D.) thanks M.S. University of Baroda for a research assistantship.

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Received, May 16, 1967.

10. V. M. Rodionov, T. V. Mackinskaya, and V. M., Belikov; *J. Gen. Chem. (Russian)*, 1948, **18**, 917.
11. G. Ponzio, *Gazz. Chim. Italy.*, 1921, **51**, (II), 218.